

PERIPHRASES AND THEIR USAGE IN MASS MEDIA AND LITERATURE

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Abstract. *This article is devoted to the use of periphrasis in mass media and Literature. The article analyzes the use of periphrasis in mass media and Literature with examples.*

Key words. *Periphrasis, stylistics, mass media, literature, ironic.*

**ПЕРИФРАЗЫ И ИХ ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕ В СРЕДСТВАХ МАССОВОЙ
ИНФОРМАЦИИ И ЛИТЕРАТУРЕ**

Аннотация. *Данная статья посвящена использованию перифразов в средствах массовой информации и литературе. В статье на примерах анализируется употребление перифразов в средствах массовой информации и литературе.*

Ключевые слова. *Перифраз, стилистика, средства массовой информации, литература, ирония.*

INTRODUCTION

One of the most complex and at the same time important phenomena in linguistics today is such a stylistic device as periphrasis. In the field of terminological definition of periphrasis, some contradictions arise due to the fact that this phenomenon is used in various fields, such as logic, literary criticism, stylistics, rhetoric and even music; this does not allow periphrasis to be defined only as a subject of linguistics.

Among other things, the definition of the term is complicated by the variability in the pronunciation of this word; in the literature, some variants of the name are given: paraphrase, paraphrase, paraphrase, periphrasis, periphrasis, the meaning of which in various dictionaries is defined as “retelling”, “roundabout speech”. Some researchers believe that the word “periphrasis” comes from the Greek “periphrasis”, but most scientists suggest that this word appeared as a result of borrowing a French term.[1]

I.V.Arnold interprets the periphrasis in accordance with this idea as a combination expressing its main features or a descriptive phrase used to express the definition of the word instead of the name of the subject [2]

According to A.T.Rubailo, studied paraphrasing as one of the artistic means of language and understood it as a process of renaming. He emphasizes that the phenomenon of paraphrasing is formed by one of the methods of semantic migration-the method of metonymy: We are talking about Moscow, but in certain cases: the capital works for the whole world, the heart of the country of socialism. You can say a military parade, a parade of vigorous youth of our Motherland, a sports parade, a demonstration of our invincible power. It is not difficult to see that such expressions are nothing but a kind of extended metonymy.[3]

The scholar K. Musayev advocates the concept in this way “the concept of such renaming of an object with a phrase is easily understood by the reader within the context”. The scholar claims that with periphrases some certain words, expression and set phrases can be replaced by other words that are understood to the reader or listener. Additionally, according to Musayev, words of periphrases examples are understood even without context, as they are synonymic versions of the words. [4]

Through the research of Yu. E. Cherednichenko, the Russian and English explanatory periphrasis has power to express irony. The texts of works of art use explanatory periphrases with elements of irony (28% of the total number of explanatory periphrases), denoting persons (gender, family relationships, external data), human activities, household items, animals and insects, topoi: incontrovertible evidence of his guilt/irrefutable evidence of his guilt, contraband/smuggling, the destination of socks, the mortal remains of a rookery, a military springboard of love, a glitched friend of the brains of humanity (designation of household items through explanatory and ironic periphrases); lug-head chewer of ironing boards / stupid eater of ironing boards; a person without a passport and of a completely non-human nationality (designation of insects/animals through explanatory and ironic periphrases); cockroach paradise (explanatory and ironic periphrastic designation of topos).[5]

To sum up, periphrasis is derived from the Greek word “retelling” or “roundabout”. In addition, a periphrasis is a process of renaming something without using its name directly, sometimes through irony or artistic.

Usage Periphrasis In Mass Media and Literature

In the mass media and literature, paraphrasing proper nouns is widely used to attract the attention of the reader or viewer to the desired topic, to enrich the color of the work or show, to enhance it, to avoid monotony.

In today's fast-paced world, everything has become faster, so the sources of information used to be only television, radio, and newspapers, but now it's the Internet. There is hardly a house

without Internet access, so the amount of information and its becoming obsolete in two or three hours leads to strong competition for mass media resources. Television and other mass media resources today resort to paraphrasing more than ever to attract attention and attract the audience, especially in the titles of programs and reports. This process can often be found in the periphrasis of proper nouns. Intriguing, exaggerated and ironical headlines attract viewers' attention more, for example, instead of the name of a simple criminal "The Savage Killer" surprised everyone in court today, the residents of "Waterless Village" appealed to our television for help, "Vampire Village" is it true?" "Knowledgeable Student" received "The Spark". Uzbek famous artist "Prima donna" is suing with whom else? Television and shows operate on the basis of ratings, the above alarming and intriguing paraphrased headlines make people interested in watching the show.

In literature, paraphrasing proper nouns is widely used to direct the reader's attention and focus to a person or place. Characters in many literary works are remembered by readers not by their names, but by paraphrased names. For instance, Gafur Gulam's famous work "Shum bola" [6]. In the story the hero's name didn't mentioned insist of the name is used the periphrasis "Karavoy" which based on his appearance and the title of the work "Shum bola" based on his behaviour. The hero's name is not mentioned in the work.

Yulduz Usmonova is called "Primaddona"[7] of Uzbek pop music. To this day, the singer of innumerable hit songs, people give her such a periphrasis because the tunes of her songs have a place in the hearts, at the moment there is no female singer who can equal his level on the Uzbek Stage.

Alisher Navoi, G'azal mulking sultoni[8] (The king of the treasure of G'azal poetry, is one of the writers who first created works in Turkish and gave an indelible legacy to Uzbek literature. The Gazals written by Alisher Navoi have a very deep meaning and are still studied and sung to the tunes. In addition, Alisher Navoi was called "Adolatparvar" and "Elparvar" among the people, because this person was remembered not only as a poet and writer in history but also as an honest official in public service.

Of course, the periphrasis given to a person or any proper noun cannot reveal it completely, the proof of this is that several periphrasis are used about a place or person, and the corresponding periphrasis is used depending on the topic. For example, any country can have cultural, economic, financial, military, technical, architectural and other advantages over other countries.

Exaggerated, ironically and cutting paraphrases are more likely to attract attention than positive ones. Mass media uses them for attraction. If we see or read information with one positive and one negative title or name of famous celebrity, it is clear that we start search for watching or reading with a negative or exaggerated one.

To illustrate this, when Donald Trump won became the president of the USA, he was almost the dominant theme in all publishing with various expressions of periphrasis to describe him, especially ironically. “Orange Agent” this periphrasis is a play on Trump's skin tone and also references the herbicide used during the Vietnam War, which has had long-lasting negative effects on health and the environment. etc., [9]. Big Rocket Man, Duke Nukem, The Wrath of Con, The Flipmat, Vanilla ISIS, The Lyin’ King, The Lord of the Blings, Darth Hater, Uncle Scam, The Banana Republican; Small donkey (Winston Churchill).

The Plastic King (Michael Jackson)[10] his periphrasis was sometimes used to criticize Jackson's numerous cosmetic surgeries and changes in appearance, suggesting that he had become obsessed with altering his looks. Wacko Jacko, Applehead

War Machine (USA) The USA is sometimes referred to as a “war machine” due to its significant military capabilities, interventionist foreign policy, and extensive history of involvement in conflicts around the world. The Obscure Nation, The Big Bully

Pollution Nation (China) To sum up, periphrasis is derived from the Greek word “retelling” or “roundabout”. In addition, a periphrasis is a process of renaming something without using its name directly, sometimes through irony or artistic. China's rapid industrialization has led to severe air, water, and soil pollution in many areas, earning it this derogatory periphrasis.

Land of Dictats(Germany) this periphrasis plays on the German word “Diktat” (dictate) and can be used to criticize Germany’s perceived dominance or heavy-handed influence within the European Union, particularly in economic matters.

CONCLUSION

Periphrases have been extensively studied by numerous scholars. The key concept revolves around renaming through descriptive means. Yu. E. Cherednichenko, a scientist, revealed that periphrasis can carry an ironic undertone. ARubello, through scientific analysis, suggested that periphrasis holds an artistic significance, seen as a form of renaming. Paraphrases are widely utilized in media and literature, especially in today's digital age where captivating the audience is challenging without the use of exaggerated and ironic headlines. Periphrases are essential in capturing public interest in the contemporary information world.

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